

1 **Abstract**

2 The detection of the highly toxic per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances, PFAS,
3 constitutes a challenging task in terms of developing a generic method that could be
4 rapid and applicable simultaneously to both long and short-chain PFAS at ppt
5 concentration level. In the present study, the method introduced by the USA
6 Environmental Protection Agency, EPA, to detect surfactants, using methylene blue,
7 MB, which is identified an ideal candidate for PFAS-MB ion pairing, is extended at
8 the lowest concentration range by a simple additional step that involves the dissociation
9 of the ion pairs in water. In this work, Surface Enhanced Raman Scattering, SERS, is
10 applied via Ag nanocolloidal suspensions to probe MB and indirectly either/or both
11 short-chain (perfluorobutyric acid, PFBA) and long-chain (perfluorooctanoic acid,
12 PFOA) PFAS in the range of 5 ppt. This method, which can be further optimized to
13 sub-ppt level *via* a custom-made SERS-PFAS dedicated Raman system, offers the
14 possibility to be applied to either specific PFAS (both short and long-chain) in a
15 targeted analysis or to total PFAS in a non-targeted analysis at very low detection limits,
16 following any type of MB detection method in aqueous solutions and obviously with
17 any type of SERS substrate.

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19 **Keywords:** Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), Surface Enhanced Raman
20 Scattering (SERS), ion pairing

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28 **1. Introduction**

29 PFAS are classified as environmentally persistent organic pollutants (Steenland et al.,
30 2009; Genuis et al., 2010; Jane L Espartero et al., 2022). The EPA has listed nine PFAS,
31 as Resource Conservation and Recovery Act (RCRA) hazardous constituents (Dean et
32 al., 2020). Unfortunately, their environmental stability make PFAS a cumulative threat
33 with recent studies linking their exposure with health issues including endocrine
34 disruption and cancer (Fenton et al., 2021).

35 Due to their widespread application, PFAS are continually released into the
36 environment (Dadashi Firouzjaei et al., 2022) with over 95% being released into water.
37 Concentrations of both short chain, e.g. PFBA, and long chain PFAS, e.g. PFOA,
38 detected in environmental samples vary from trace levels to several micrograms per
39 liter ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) (Cheng et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2023). EPA allotted “Drinking Water
40 Health Advisories for PFOA and PFOS” at 70 parts per trillion (ppt) in 2019, and later
41 in 2022, updated even lower limits to 0.004 and 0.02 ppt, for PFOA and PFOS,
42 respectively (<https://www.epa.gov/sdwa/and-polyfluoroalkyl-substances-pfas>). Over
43 the past 190 years, numerous emerging contaminants have been identified, with PFOA
44 and PFOS receiving considerable attention based on scientific evidence and
45 publications. Between 2018 and 2019, PFOA and PFOS experienced a relatively high
46 increase rate of 18.8% and 13.6%, respectively. On the other hand, partial degradation
47 of long-chain PFAS in the environment or engineered treatment process can also result
48 in the production of short-chain PFAS which are equally or even more persistent and
49 mobile in the environment because of their higher solubility and lower sorption
50 tendency. For example, PFBA is among the most commonly used short-chain PFAS

51 and has been widely detected in aquatic environments, sometimes with levels even
52 higher than long-chain PFAS (Min and Wang, 2023).

53 However, ultra-high resolution methods and special pretreatments are currently
54 required, all of which at high costs. Current state-of-the-art techniques include analysis
55 by liquid chromatography tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), while alternatives
56 include total oxidizable precursor analysis (TOP) or total fluorine analysis by particle-
57 induced gamma-ray emission (PIGE) spectroscopy (Hagstrom et al., 2021; Winchell et
58 al., 2021; Androulakakis et al., 2022). These methods typically require off-site
59 analyses, preconcentration of the sample, extended time, high-cost and matrix-matched
60 calibration. Costs of \$300-\$600/sample are prohibitive in routine monitoring and do
61 not allow widespread analysis. On the other hand, toxicological studies has suggested
62 regulatory PFAS limits of less than one ng L⁻¹ (Scientific Committee on Health),
63 challenging to be achieved. Therefore, the cost, the challenging detection limits, the
64 limitation to analyze selected PFAS and the increased time required for the analysis,
65 limit the means of exploration and scientific understanding in an already limited field.
66 Especially, the detection of short-chain PFAS presents several challenges related to
67 their low concentrations and volatile nature. To properly evaluate human risk of PFAS
68 exposure, a faster, less expensive, and non-complicated method is needed. Due to the
69 growing urgency towards the development of a flexible and reliable PFAS detection
70 method, many research groups have focused on the use of markers-sensors (Takayose
71 et al., 2012; Zheng et al., 2019; Cheng et al., 2020; Faiz et al., 2020; Ryu et al., 2021;
72 Shanbhag et al., 2022; Park et al., 2024). For instance, Cennamo et al. have used a
73 molecularly imprinted polymer on a plasmonic plastic optical fiber to detect PFOS and
74 PFOA in the ppb (ng mL⁻¹) level (Cennamo et al., 2018). On the other hand, very
75 recently fluorous polyaniline in an electrical lateral flow sensor was used for the

76 detection of PFOA with a detection at 400 ppt (ng mL^{-1}) (Park et al., 2024). Even if to
77 date, there is a limited number of inventions, which are focused on fluorescent probes,
78 electrochemical sensors (Shanbhag et al., 2024) and high performance liquid
79 chromatography, it is encouraging that at the moment a growing number of studies are
80 provided.

81 SERS offers several advantages as an analytical tool, including high sensitivity,
82 selectivity, stability, multiplexing capability, versatility, and non-destructive nature
83 making it a powerful analytical technique (Mahurin et al., 2011; Littleford et al., 2017;
84 Mosier-Boss, 2017a, b; Andrikaki et al., 2018; Bai et al., 2019; Viehrig et al., 2020;
85 Krajczewski et al., 2021) with great potential for pollutant detection (Li et al., 2014;
86 Moldovan et al., 2021). SERS is based on the great enhancement of the inelastic light
87 scattering of molecules (by factors of up to 10^8 or even greater in some cases), allowing
88 even a single-molecule detection, when the analyte is “adsorbed” onto the surface of
89 noble metal nanoparticles (MNPs), such as Ag or Au. In particular, towards the
90 detection of PFAS, SERS could address important limitations, being rapid, generic and
91 easily applicable for the detection of either short or long-chain PFAS following one
92 protocol and without the requirements of preconcentrating/pretreatment of the samples,
93 that existing methods require. However, regardless of the urgent need of ultrasensitive
94 and rapid detection, to date, only a few recent studies exist on SERS-based detection of
95 PFAS (Fang et al., 2016; Bai et al., 2022; M.B et al., 2023; McDonnell et al., 2023;
96 Park et al., 2023). This is probably related to combinatorial characteristics of PFAS,
97 such as no available interacting sites due to molecular structure, hydrophobicity,
98 surfactant properties. For instance, Fang and his co-workers prepared a SERS substrate
99 using nanosphere lithography Ag and graphene oxide (GO) membrane, in which the
100 ion pairs between the dye ethyl violet and the firefighting foams acted as the probe for

101 the SERS detection achieving a 50 ppb detection limit (Fang et al., 2016). On the other
102 hand, when a plasmonic superstructure based on Ag NPs and silica was fabricated by
103 laser near-field reduction for the detection of PFOA, the detection limit was 11 ppb (Bai
104 et al., 2022). Ion-pairing extraction combined with detection methods (e.g.
105 spectrophotometry) has been previously utilized for the quantification of different
106 molecules including some PFAS. Ion-pairing reagents, such as dyes, are compounds
107 that can form ion pairs with PFAS molecules, facilitating their extraction from an
108 aqueous phase into an organic solvent phase (i.e. chloroform). In this context, the dye-
109 PFAS ion pairs are transferred into the organic phase, while the excess of the dye
110 remains in the aquatic phase since it is insoluble in the organic phase (Sharma et al.,
111 1989; Menger et al., 2022). The EPA has developed a method using MB active
112 substances (MBAS) for detecting surfactants in drinking water, surface water, and
113 domestic and industrial wastewater. After that point, several efforts have been made
114 towards that concept in which alternative dyes were examined, exhibiting however
115 similar or worst performance (Al Amin et al., 2020; Shanbhag et al., 2024). One of the
116 advantages of the extraction procedure established by the EPA is the ability to
117 selectively isolate the PFAS-dye ion pairs to the chloroform solution, whilst at the same
118 time any other co-existing substances remaining to the aqueous phase. This is very
119 important since interference phenomena can be avoided.

120 In the present study, the method introduced by the US EPA for the indirect detection of
121 the presence of PFAS anionic surfactants by the addition of the cationic dye MB
122 through ion pair formation extracted in chloroform is extended by a simple additional
123 step involving the dissociation of ion pairs in water. This approach provides firstly the
124 critical flexibility to develop a generic detection of applying a single method across a
125 wide range of both short and long chain PFAS, or even on total PFAS, while in parallel

126 extending the possibility towards low detection limits. In this study, we adopted the
127 application of SERS utilizing Ag nanocolloidal solutions as plasmonic substrate to
128 probe the detection of MB attributed to the dye, enabling ion-pair formation with PFAS,
129 and indirectly either/or both short-chain (PFBA) and long-chain (PFOA) at a ppt level.
130 This approach may pave the way for a generic SERS based approach and enable the
131 detection of PFAS at even lower detection limits (see EPA) with a potentially even
132 more optimized SERS detection method. A note is made of the fact that due to the
133 generic character of this approach any analytical method able to probe MB at the lowest
134 concentration levels can be also applied.

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136 **2. Experimental section**

137 2.1 Chemicals and reagents

138 The chemicals and reagents including methylene blue (MB, CAS No.: 122965-43-9),
139 citric acid (CAS No.:77-92-9), Sodium citrate tribasic dihydrate (CAS Number: 6132-
140 04-3), perfluorooctanoic acid (CAS No.:335-67-1), (perfluorobutyric acid (CAS
141 No.:375-22-4) and silver nitrate (AgNO_3 , CAS Number: 7761-88-8) used in the present
142 study were all purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used without additional purification.
143 Chloroform (Chloroform, HPLC, 99.8% min., ACS) was purchased by Fisher
144 scientific. For the preparation of the solutions triple distilled (MilliQwater, Millipore
145 system) water was used.

146 2.2 Extraction of ion pairs and methodology

147 For the extraction of the ion pairs from the aqueous phase in the organic phase
148 (chloroform, CHCl_3) a previous established EPA method was followed (Sharma et al.,
149 1989). Briefly, the aqueous phase comprised of 2 mL of a MB solution 10^{-3} M (in
150 excess), 2 mL of a buffer solution (citric acid/sodium citrate, 10^{-2} M, pH=5) and 4 mL

151 of a PFAS solution at various concentrations. Subsequently the aqueous solution was
152 mixed with 20 mL of chloroform and the ion pairs PFAS-MB were transferred to the
153 organic phase (Fig. S1). Blanc solution was also prepared for normalizing the extraction
154 process; in the aqueous phase, 4 mL of triple distilled water was added instead of 4 mL
155 of PFAS solution. The intervention to this EPA method in this study was the
156 dissociation of these ion-pairs existing in the CHCl_3 phase into aqueous medium, taking
157 into account that the dye (i.e. MB) has very low detection limits with SERS when it is
158 diluted in water. More details about the impact of dissociation are provided in the
159 results.

160 2.3 UV/Vis measurements

161 UV-Vis absorption spectra were obtained with a double beam Lambda UV/Vis/NIR
162 Spectrometer of Hitachi (U-3000). The spectra were recorded from 800 to 400 nm with
163 a slit of 0.5 nm.

164 2.4 Raman measurements

165 SERS spectra were obtained on a T-64000 spectrometer (ISA-Horiba group) using a
166 He-Ne laser (Optronics Technologies S.A. model HLA-20P, 20 mW) operating at 632.8
167 nm. The specific laser line at 632.8 nm was selected to generate Surface Enhanced
168 Resonance Raman Scattering, SERRS, due to the respective absorption of MB probed
169 by UV-Vis absorbance at $\sim 640 \text{ nm}^{-1}$. The power of the laser beam measured at the
170 sample was 5 mW. The Raman system was used in the single spectrograph
171 configuration for the collection, analysis and detection of the scattered light. The
172 colloids used to collect the SERS spectra were prepared by the chemical reduction of
173 silver nitrate with sodium citrate according to a modified Lee and Meisel procedure
174 described previously (Lee and Meisel, 1982). A right-angle Raman scattered light
175 collection geometry was adopted, the best for liquids and nanocolloidal solutions

176 (Anastasopoulos et al., 2017). All measurements were conducted in triplicate and the
177 mean values are provided.

178 **3. Results and discussion**

179 3.1 Detection of PFAS-MB ion pairs in CHCl₃

180 For the detection of PFAS-MB ion pairs, UV/Vis spectroscopy was applied in the
181 solution of the organic phase (CHCl₃) after the extraction of the ion pairs from the
182 aqueous phase (Fig. S2a). As a case study of short chain PFAS, PFBA-MB ion pairs
183 were quantified using the absorption maximum at ~650 nm attributed to MB. The
184 PFBA initial concentration in the aqueous phase is the controlling factor to the final
185 concentration of the PFBA-MB ion pairs in the organic phase. In this context, a linear
186 dependence between the value of the maximum absorption and the PFBA-MB
187 concentration in the organic phase was observed (Fig. S2b) resulting the corresponding
188 calibration curve. Using UV/Vis, the detection limit for PFBA-MB ion pairs was found
189 to be approximately 0.05 ppm (mg L⁻¹). The methodology was utilized for a
190 representative long-chain PFAS, and the PFOA-MB system exhibited analogous
191 behaviour (Fig. S3) with a detection limit of 1 ppm.

192 SERS has been widely utilized for the detection of analytes at very low detection limits
193 (Sharma et al., 2012; Mathioudakis et al., 2020). In particular, for the detection of the
194 MB in water, SERS has been previously applied with a detection limits down to 32 ppt
195 (Mikac et al., 2015) and 25 ppt (pg mL⁻¹) (Anastasopoulos et al., 2017). As it is shown
196 in Fig. 1 following the SERS detection of MB in water detection limits down to
197 LOQ=25 ppt (mg L⁻¹) is achievable. The SERS spectra of MB aqueous solutions of
198 known concentrations were recorded and the corresponding calibration curves were
199 plotted based on the peak area of the characteristic peak of MB at 1620 cm⁻¹ (C-C ring
200 stretching).

201 In this context, SERS spectra of the chloroform solution containing the PFAS-MB ion
202 pairs were recorded (Fig. 1). The SERS spectra profile recorded using the plasmonic
203 colloidal solution are identical with the corresponding ones used for the detection of
204 MB aqueous solutions, indicating that MB is being individually detected and not as an
205 ion pair. A possible mechanism that explains the above is the diffusion of the MB from
206 CHCl_3 into the SERS aqueous colloidal suspension where it interacts with Ag NPs and
207 is being detected in analogy with the experiments performed for its
208 detection/quantification from its aqueous solutions (Fig. S4). It is evident that this
209 detection of MB diffusion from CHCl_3 is not as effective as it would be with easily
210 accessible molecules of MB in a water solution instead of CHCl_3 . This is also supported
211 by the fact that the Raman spectrum of the ion-pairing chloroform solution (initial
212 concentration of PFBA= 20 ppm/20 mg L^{-1}) compared with the corresponding of MB
213 in water ($C=300$ ppm/300 mgL^{-1}) or with the SERS spectrum of the PFBA-MB ion-
214 pairing solution in chloroform (initial concentration of PFBA= 20 ppm/20 mg L^{-1}) are
215 similar but not identical (section S5, Fig. S5). Nevertheless, it is apparent that the SERS
216 signal of MB in MB-PFAS ion pairs is dependent on the PFAS concentration (either
217 PFBA or PFOA), and detection could be achieved down to 100 ppt (pg mL^{-1}) and 5 ppb
218 (ng mL^{-1}) for PFBA and PFOA, respectively. Since the diffusion of MB from
219 chloroform to the colloidal suspensions may not be efficient, the above mentioned
220 methodology can be furthermore improved by controlling the dissociation of the ion-
221 pairs into aqueous solutions before performing the SERS measurements; it may as well
222 be optimized aiming the reduction of the attainable detection limits.

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226 **Fig. 1.** The SERS spectra of the PFBA-MB (a) and PFOA-MB (c) ion pairs in
 227 chloroform after extraction from the aqueous phase. In the spectra, the reference
 228 spectrum of the “blanc” solution was subtracted. The SERS calibration curve of PFBA-
 229 MB (b) and PFOA-MB (d) ion pairs in chloroform are shown based on the peak area
 230 of the characteristic peak at 1620 cm^{-1} ; insets depict the SERS calibration curves at the
 231 lower concentration values. Light/dark grey regions indicate the low concentration
 232 range that can be quantified by UV-Vis/SERS respectively.

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234 3.2 Detection of MB after dissociation of PFAS-MB ion pairs in aqueous solutions

235 The detection of MB in water solutions with SERS, as already invoked, has been
 236 previously intensely examined since it is classified as a toxic organic pollutant in water
 237 and low detection limits are well received (Anastasopoulos et al., 2017). Therefore,

238 considering that the detection limits in the chloroform was much higher than the ones
239 expected for MB in aqueous solutions, we explored the possibility to dissociate into
240 water the PFAS-MB ion pairs existing in the chloroform. In this context, different types
241 of aqueous solutions were introduced (i.e. triple distilled water, 0.1N NaCl, 0.1M HCl
242 and 0.1M NaOH) towards the maximization of the PFBA-MB and PFOA-MB ion pairs
243 dissociation (Fig. S6). It was revealed that the use of H₂O or 0.1M HCl (Fig. S6a, Fig.
244 S6b) were the most effective to transfer MB into the water phase. Therefore, in order
245 to simplify the process and avoid potential MB degradation due to HCl (indicated in
246 previous studies (Scientific Committee on Health)), H₂O was used for subsequent
247 dissociation experiments. In addition, the amount of water used for the dissociation was
248 also evaluated. In particular, mixtures between the CHCl₃ phase (in which ion pairs
249 exist) and water with ratio 1:1 v/v, 1:0.5 v/v and 1:2 v/v, respectively, were tested (Fig.
250 S7a, S7b). It is apparent that an extended and rapid dissociation occurs in all ratios,
251 however the 1:1 ratio was chosen since the 1:2 ratio gives worse detection limit for the
252 dissociated amount of MB, whilst the 1:0.5 ratio may not be sufficient for completely
253 dissociation for different range of PFAS concentrations. In order to further verify the
254 dissociation efficiency of the process, it was also tested if the addition of a double PFAS
255 initial concentration at a double volume of water during dissociation has a comparable
256 SERS signal (Fig. S7c). It is evident that the SERS spectrum after dissociation of ion
257 pairs with 0.02 ppm initial concentration of PFBA with double amount of water (1:2
258 v/v ratio) during the dissociation process, is similar to the SERS spectrum after
259 dissociation of ion pairs with 0.01 ppm initial concentration of PFBA by utilizing the
260 conventional 1:1 v/v ratio. This was also noticed for a set of lower PFBA initial
261 concentration.

262 An additional crosscheck of the dissociation efficiency was performed by utilizing
263 multiple “washing” with water of the ion-pair chloroform solution. Specifically, after
264 following the dissociation procedure by mixing the ion pairs chloroform solution with
265 1:1 v/v water, the same chloroform solution (containing any remaining PFAS-MB ion
266 pairs) was mixed again with new amount of water in the 1:1 v/v ratio (Fig. S8). The
267 “washing” process was followed as needed (2-3 times). This study was performed for
268 three different PFBA initial concentration (i.e. 0.5 ppm, 0.02 and 0.001 ppm) in order
269 to record the trend at high, intermediate and low PFBA concentrations. It was noticed
270 that only a small amount of ion pairs remains in chloroform after the dissociation
271 process in all cases. In particular, as the PFBA initial concentration is increased, further
272 “washing” is required with a remaining however amount of ion pairs in chloroform of
273 less than 2% of the total amount of ion pairs detected in the dissociated water solution.
274 Most importantly, at very low initial PFBA concentrations dissociation was almost
275 complete at once.

276 3.3 Comparison of MB detection after dissociation and through ion-pairs in CHCl_3

277 Based on the above findings, the dissociation approach was followed for different
278 concentrations of PFAS in order to evaluate the dissociation approach compared to the
279 SERS detection of the ion pairs in the CHCl_3 solution after the extraction. Apparently,
280 the dissociation occurs at a wide range of PFBA initial concentrations, and the vast
281 majority of ion pairs existing in the chloroform phase are dissociated into water. It is
282 also noticeable that if the SERS spectra of the dissociated ion pairs and the SERS
283 spectra of the chloroform solution are compared, a much higher SERS signal (and
284 therefore better limit of detection) is noticed in the dissociated pairs in the aqueous
285 phase (Fig. 2). In other words, the miscible water solution of the dissociated pairs and
286 the aqueous colloidal SERS substrate promote the rapid interaction of the NPs and the

287 MB molecules. On the contrary, the immiscible chloroform phase with the aqueous
288 phase of the SERS substrate inhibits the effective interaction of the NPs with the total
289 amount of the MB or rather due to the incomplete dissociation of the ion pairs in the
290 vicinity of the charged particles (Bergström and Grillo, 2014). Following this trend, the
291 detection limit that could be achieved by applying SERS analyzing the initial
292 chloroform solution containing the ion pairs was 5 ppb and 100 ppt for PFOA and
293 PFBA, respectively, while following a subsequent dissociation of the ion pairs in water,
294 the SERS detection resulted a LOD down to 5 ppt for PFBA.
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296
297 **Fig. 2.** The SERS spectra of dissociated PFBA-MB at various PFBA initial
298 concentrations after dissociation. The SERS spectra of the remaining PFAS-MB in
299 CHCl₃ and the ones of ion pairs in chloroform before dissociation are also shown.
300

301 3.4 Intervalvalidation of the accuracy following the dissociated approach and comparison
302 with existing PFAS detection SERS studies

303 In order to evaluate the accuracy of the proposed dissociation approach towards better
304 detection limits, we have performed two parallel experiments (Fig. 3). In the first one
305 the SERS spectra at different MB solutions in water at different concentrations were
306 recorded. In a second step, the entire extraction procedure and dissociation process was
307 followed by adding various known concentrations of PFBA in the first aqueous mixture
308 of MB with PFBA. This SERS signal was irrelevant to the simultaneous presence of
309 PFBA in the MB aqueous solution (Fig. S9). The two calibration curves (Fig. 3b and c)
310 are in close proximity with a low Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) value of 0.02,
311 verifying firstly the 1:1 ion pairing between the molecules of MB and the PFAS
312 molecules, and secondly the effectiveness of the dissociation in the last step of the
313 process. Based on all the above, in an alternative verification scenario of the extraction
314 method, which is now based on the dissociation of the ion pairs, the initial amount of
315 PFAS has only to be compared with the amount of MB detected (through the calibration
316 curve) in the aqueous phase after the pairs' dissociation. In this context, the LOD's that
317 could be achieved for different PFAS could be predicted by taking into account the 1:1
318 mole ratio and the molar mass ratio of PFAS/MB (Table S1). In addition, it is important
319 that this dissociated method is independent of the PFAS substance and it could be used
320 as a generic tool for the detection of both short and long-chain PFAS, while in the case
321 of PFAS mixtures it could be also provide an estimated total amount of PFAS in a
322 mixture; the potential towards that goal is provided in section S7 (Table S1) and S8
323 (Fig. S10). The latter is promising towards the real PFAS wastewater media.

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327 **Fig. 3.** (a) The SERS spectra of dissociated PFBA-MB at different PFBA initial
 328 concentrations. The calibration curves are shown based on MB solutions in water of
 329 known MB initial concentrations (black circles) and based on the peak areas calculated
 330 for the system after dissociation of the ion-pairs expressed as moles of MB/PFBA (b)
 331 and MB/PFBA concentrations in ppm (c).

332 In Table 1, the main features and the LOD's achieved so far in the literature utilizing
 333 the SERS technique are presented, along with the ones received in this study. The
 334 significance of the present effort lies on the fact that this is the first time that a SERS
 335 method is independent of the PFAS nature and could be applied generically to different
 336 PFAS (both short chain and long chain), while simultaneously achieving very low LOD
 337 compared to the existing ones.

338 In a generic basis comparison, the SERS approach method followed in the current study
 339 is less time consuming relative to other traditional analytical methods (i.e. LC-MS/MS),
 340 offers increased selectivity as it is based on PFAS-dye ion-pairs, and requires no
 341 preconcentration of the sample. In addition, the methodology's ability to selectively
 342 isolate the PFAS-dye ion pairs in the chloroform solution, while other co-existing non-

343 cationic surfactant substances remain in the aqueous phase prohibits possible relevant
 344 interference phenomena. Nevertheless, even if the detection limit of this approach is
 345 classified among the lowest ones along with other recent attempts including
 346 electrochemical sensors or photochromic detectors (Al Amin et al., 2020; Menger et
 347 al., 2022), the detection limits that could be achieved through chromatography still
 348 prevail (i.e. <1 ppt).

349 **Table 1.** Summary of the available SERS methods for the detection of PFAS and this
 350 study.

SERS method	PFAS	LOD	Ref
Ag NPs + dye-FS-GO	PFOA PFOS	50 ppb	(Fang et al., 2016)
Ag NPs + Silica	PFOA	11 ppb to 400 ppm	(Bai et al., 2022)
Ag NPs + Graphene+Rhodamine 6G	PFOA PFOS	500 ppt 0.5 ppt	(McDonnell et al., 2023)
Silver nanograss + reaction of PFOA with p-phenylenediamine	PFOA	0.5 ppt	(Park et al., 2023)
Ag NPs + dissociated MB-PFAS ion pairs	PFBA PFOA	5 ppt	This study

351

352 3.5 Perspectives for further optimization

353 Analyzing the perspective of this SERS-based approach, it should be clarified that the
 354 present method could initiate a new path. In particular, several parameters can influence
 355 the collection of photons in Raman spectroscopy. For instance, the wavelength of the
 356 excitation laser affects the efficiency of Raman scattering since Resonance Raman
 357 scattering, which occurs when the excitation wavelength matches an electronic
 358 transition in the molecule, could lead to enhanced Raman signals. In addition, the
 359 increase of the laser power that give rise to increased scattering of the photons could
 360 result enhanced Raman signal intensity. On the other hand, is also important the
 361 configuration of the Raman system used for the photons detection, the response of the
 362 CCD detector etc. It is therefore apparent that the perspective of the SERS-based

363 detection could be expanded if these affecting factors and Raman collection could be
364 optimized. In such an attempt in this study, wanting to indicate the steppingstone
365 towards this goal, we have performed experiments by “adjusting” the collection
366 configuration of the T64000 Raman system. In particular, the Raman scattering
367 collection optics as well as the sample were placed at close proximity of the entrance
368 slit of the 3rd spectrograph of the triple T64000 Raman spectrometer. Additionally,
369 binning of the adjacent pixels of the CCD (of a factor of 4) was applied to improve the
370 signal. It is evident that MB detection of MB is further extended (Fig. 4a) being down
371 to 5 ppt compared to the limit of 25 ppt of the above mentioned strategy. The
372 comparison of an indicative spectrum of MB following the typical procedure, the
373 “adjusted” Raman collection configuration and the combination of the “adjusted”
374 system with binning (Fig. 4b) clearly indicates the perspective of SERS-approach
375 towards very low detection limits, which is not limited to a certain detection value and
376 could be expanded to even better performance depending on the photons collection
377 parameters. The parameters that a custom-made SERS-PFAS dedicated Raman system
378 can further improve allowing an optimized PFAS-MB detection at a sub-ppt level are
379 within others: (a) collecting optics which in combination with the field of focus on the
380 sample will give an image that will fit the entrance slit of the monochromator, (b)
381 higher throughput spectrograph with lower focal length (compared with the 64 cm of
382 the current system), (c) intensified CCD with high (even ~ 100%) quantum efficiency
383 in the dedicated spectral window (compared to the nominal 40% of the current system).
384 In addition, it will be insightful to investigate the efficiency of our methodology not
385 only in the context of the analysis of real wastewater and/or soil samples, but also as a
386 tool for the validation of the effectiveness of the typically used PFAS destructive
387 methods (Sharma et al., 2022; Garg et al., 2023; Kamali et al., 2023).

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400 **Fig. 4.** (a) The SERS spectra of MB at different initial concentrations; the spectra at
 401 low concentrations are highlighted in the inset, and (b) the corresponding calibration
 402 curve. (c) Comparison of the SERS spectrum of MB following the typical Raman
 403 collection procedure, the “adjusted” Raman collection configuration and the
 404 combination of the “adjusted” system with binning for 50 ppt of PFBA.

405

406 **4. Conclusions**

407 In this study, the US EPA method to detect surfactants is extended by a simple
 408 additional step that involves the dissociation of the ion pairs in water. The ability of
 409 PFAS to form ion-pairs with the MB dye was exploited and maximized with the
 410 dissociation of these ion pairs in water. A SERS based analytical method was applied
 411 to both long-chain and short-chain PFAS with the achievement of very low detection
 412 limits down to 25 ppt (25 pg mL^{-1}). The fact that this method is independent of the
 413 PFAS nature and could be applied generically to different PFAS, or even to total PFAS,
 414 while at the same time providing the possibility of very low detection limits - the SERS

415 or of any other analytical method detection limit of the dye - is promising towards its
416 potential use for wider exploitation. Among our next steps is to validate the present
417 methodology for the investigation of real wastewater and soil samples but also to apply
418 this detection method for the validation of the efficacy of PFAS destructive methods
419 used.

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673 **List of Figures Captions**

674 **Fig. 1.** The SERS spectra of the PFBA-MB (a) and PFOA-MB (c) ion pairs in
675 chloroform after extraction from the aqueous phase. In the spectra, the reference
676 spectrum of the “blanc” solution was subtracted. The SERS calibration curve of PFBA-
677 MB (b) and PFOA-MB (d) ion pairs in chloroform are shown based on the peak area
678 of the characteristic peak at 1620 cm^{-1} ; insets depict the SERS calibration curves at the
679 lower concentration values. Light/dark grey regions indicate the low concentration
680 range that can be quantified by UV-Vis/SERS respectively.

681 **Fig. 2.** The SERS spectra of dissociated PFBA-MB at various PFBA initial
682 concentrations after dissociation. The SERS spectra of the remaining PFAS-MB in
683 CHCl_3 and the ones of ion pairs in chloroform before dissociation are also shown.

684 **Fig. 3.** (a) The SERS spectra of dissociated PFBA-MB at different PFBA initial
685 concentrations. The calibration curves are shown based on MB solutions in water of
686 known MB initial concentrations (black circles) and based on the peak areas calculated
687 for the system after dissociation of the ion-pairs expressed as moles of MB/PFBA (b)
688 and MB/PFBA concentrations in ppm (c).

689 **Fig. 4.** (a) The SERS spectra of MB at different initial concentrations; the spectra at
690 low concentrations are highlighted in the inset, and (b) the corresponding calibration
691 curve. (c) Comparison of the SERS spectrum of MB following the typical Raman
692 collection procedure, the “adjusted” Raman collection configuration and the
693 combination of the “adjusted” system with binning for 50 ppt of PFBA.

694

1 **S1 Procedure for the extraction of the ion pairs**

2 Following the EPA method, in this analytical procedure the ion-pairs are transferred from an
3 aqueous phase where the PFAS co-exist with an excess of dissolved MB, to the miscible phase of
4 CHCl_3 where only the ion-pairs exist.

5
6 **Figure S1.** Schematic representation of the procedure followed for the extraction of PFAS-MB
7 ion pairs into the organic phase.

8 During this study, several parameters related to the extraction process were examined in order to
9 make sure that the existing proposed method is the optimum one. In these terms, experiments were
10 conducted both in the absence/presence of citrate buffer (which resulted different pH of the
11 solution) and at different ratios of the PFAS/MB/citrate solutions, and under different mixing
12 times. From this study we concluded that the presence of citrate buffer was critical for the
13 successful extraction of the ion pairs to the chloroform, while under these conditions, mixing time
14 did not seem to be extremely important. In addition, the dye concentration is important to be in
15 significant excess compared to the PFAS concentration for the successful and rapid isolation of
16 the ion pairs to the chloroform phase.

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19 **S2 Detection of PFOA-MB ion pairs in CHCl₃ using UV/Vis**

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21

22 **Figure S2.** (a) The UV/Vis spectra of the PFBA-MB ion pairs in chloroform after extraction from
23 the aqueous phase. The spectra have been normalized using as reference the “blanc” solution. (b)

24 The calibration curve of PFBA-MB ion pairs in chloroform.

25 **S3 Detection of PFOA-MB ion pairs in CHCl₃ using UV/Vis**

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27

28 **Figure S3.** (a) The UV/Vis spectra of the PFOA-MB ion pairs in chloroform after extraction from
 29 the aqueous phase. The spectra have been normalized using as reference the “blanc” solution. (b)

30 The calibration curve of PFOA-MB ion pairs in chloroform.

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33 S4. Detection of MB in water

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36 **Figure S4.** The SERS spectra of MB solutions in water at different MB initial concentrations

37 (excitation line 632 nm).

38 S5 Comparison of Raman and SERS spectra

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40 **Figure S5.** The SERS and Raman spectra of the PFBA-MB ion pairs in chloroform (initial
41 concentration of PFBA= 20 ppm) after extraction from the aqueous phase. The Raman spectrum
42 of MB in TDW (MB=300 ppm) is also shown for comparison. The excitation was performed using
43 the 785 nm line to avoid the fluorescence co-existing in the conventional Raman spectrum.

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46 **S6 Dissociation of the ion-pairs**

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49 **Figure S6.** The SERS spectra of dissociated PFBA-MB (a) and PFOA-MB (b) ion pairs in water
50 at different aqueous solutions (i.e. triple distilled water, 0.1N NaCl, 0.1M HCl and 0.1M NaOH)
51 between the CHCl_3 phase (in which ion pairs exist) and water with ratio 1:1 v/v. The SERS spectra
52 of the remaining PFAS-MB in CHCl_3 are also shown for the evaluation of the dissociation
53 efficiency.

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56 **Figure S7.** The SERS spectra of dissociated PFBA-MB (a) and PFOA-MB (b) ion pairs in water
57 at different ratio mixtures between the CHCl_3 phase (in which ion pairs exist) and water with ratio
58 1:1 v/v, 1:0.5 v/v and 1:2 v/v, respectively. The SERS spectra of the remaining PFAS-MB in
59 CHCl_3 are also shown for the evaluation of the dissociation efficiency. (c) Comparison of SERS
60 spectrum after dissociation of ion pairs with 0.02 ppm (or 0.002 ppm) initial concentration of
61 PFBA with double amount of water (1:2 v/v ratio) during the dissociation process and SERS
62 spectrum after dissociation of ion pairs with 0.01 ppm (or 0.001 ppm) initial concentration of
63 PFBA by utilizing the conventional 1:1 v/v ratio.

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70 **Figure S8.** The SERS spectra of dissociated PFBA-MB at PFBA initial concentration (a) 0.001
 71 ppm, (b) 0.02 ppm and (c) 0.5 ppm after multiple “washing” with water of the ion-pair chloroform
 72 solution with ratio 1:1 v/v; the corresponding calculated MB concentration values based on the
 73 calibration curve of MB in water are also shown for comparison. In addition, the SERS spectra of
 74 the remaining PFAS-MB in CHCl_3 are presented for the evaluation of the dissociation efficiency.

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76 **Figure S9.** The SERS spectra of the MB in water (8×10^{-11} moles) and the corresponding SERS

77 spectrum when isomolar quantity of PFBA (8×10^{-11} moles) is also present in the solution.

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92 **S7 Lowest detection limits (LODs) calculation**

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94 **Table S1.** Predicted lowest detection limits for different PFAS based on the dissociation
95 approach in MB-PFAS pairing.

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PFAS	Name	Classification	Predicted LOD (pg/mL, ppt)
PFBA	Perfluorobutanoic acid	Short chain	17 (25ppt due to the LOD of MB in water)
PFPeA	Perfluoropentanoic acid	Short chain	21 (25ppt due to the LOD of MB in water)
PFHxA	Perfluorohexanoic acid	Short chain	25
PFHpA	Perfluoroheptanoic acid	Long chain	28
PFOA	Perfluorooctanoic acid	Long chain	32
PFNA	Perfluorononanoic acid	Long chain	36
PFDA	Perfluorodecanoic acid	Long chain	40
PFUdA	Perfluoroundecanoic acid	Long chain	44
PFDoDA	Perfluorododecanoic acid	Long chain	48
PFTTrDA	Perfluorotridecanoic acid	Long chain	52

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110 **S8 Potential towards mixtures detection efficiency**

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113 **Figure S10.** The SERS spectra after the 1:1 v/v dissociation in water from chloroform solutions

114 of PFOA, PFBA or PFOA/PFBA (1:1 v/v ratio between the two PFAS). The moles of PFAS in all

115 cases are the same for direct comparison.

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